

Problems, solutions and development prospects of modernization of irrigation systems in agriculture in Uzbekistan.

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Abstract: The article analyzes the importance of irrigation systems in agriculture, existing challenges, and the potential to increase productivity and efficiency through water-saving technologies. The findings highlight the prospects for modernizing irrigation systems and managing water resources effectively.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada qishloq xo'jaligida sug'orish tizimlarining ahamiyati, mavjud muammolari va suv tejovchi texnologiyalar orqali hosildorlik va samaradorlikni oshirish imkoniyatlari tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot natijalari sug'orish tizimlarini modernizatsiya qilish va suv resurslarini samarali boshqarish istiqbollarini ochib beradi.

Аннотация: В статье анализируется значение ирригационных систем в сельском хозяйстве, существующие проблемы и возможности повышения урожайности и эффективности с использованием водосберегающих технологий. Результаты исследования показывают перспективы модернизации ирригационных систем и рационального управления водными ресурсами.

Keywords: agriculture, irrigation systems, water resources, drip irrigation, productivity, water conservation, irrigation efficiency

Kalit so'zlar: qishloq xo'jaligi, sug'orish tizimlari, suv resurslari, tomchilatib sug'orish, hosildorlik, suv tejash, irrigatsiya samaradorligi

Ключевые слова: сельское хозяйство, ирригационные системы, водные ресурсы, капельное орошение, урожайность, водосбережение, эффективность ирригации

ENTRANCE

Agriculture is one of the main sectors of the economy of Uzbekistan, accounting for about 25 percent of the country's gross domestic product (GDP). The sustainable development of this sector largely depends on the rational use of water resources, namely the efficiency of irrigation systems. Since a large part of the country's territory is located in arid climate conditions, and more than 80 percent of agricultural production is carried out on irrigated land. Therefore, water resource management, the introduction of water-saving technologies, and the modernization of outdated irrigation infrastructure are among the most urgent issues of our time.

As President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev noted, "saving water resources and their effective management are the key to sustainable development in agriculture" [1]. This idea determines the main directions of water management reforms being implemented in Uzbekistan. In recent years, water-saving technologies, drip and sprinkler irrigation systems have been widely introduced in the country, which not only reduces water consumption, but also increases productivity. In this regard, the modernization of irrigation systems is an important factor in increasing the competitiveness of not only the agricultural sector, but also the entire economy.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

In recent years, a lot of scientific research has been conducted in Uzbekistan on water resources management and irrigation system reform. In particular, Karimov and Yuladasheva in their study analyzed the water-saving efficiency of drip irrigation technology in Uzbek conditions, emphasizing that this method can reduce water consumption by up to 40 percent. [2].

Also, researchers such as Kuryozev Kuryoz and Nurmukhamedov Sanjar have noted in their scientific works that the introduction of digital management systems in water management can increase the fairness and efficiency of water distribution [3].

The "Sustainable Water Resources Management" project implemented in Uzbekistan by the European Union and the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) emphasizes the need to reduce water consumption and increase the environmental culture of farmers [4].

At the same time, local scientists - researchers such as Valuev, Kholboev, and Murodov - also made recommendations on improving the reclamation of irrigation systems, restoring drainage systems, and reducing water losses [5].

METHODOLOGY

The study used a comprehensive analytical method, statistical analysis, comparative and systematic approaches. The main data were analyzed based on reports from the Ministry of Water Resources of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the State Statistics Agency, and the UN FAO. Also, indicators such as water consumption, yield level, and maintenance costs were studied to determine the efficiency of irrigation systems. The analysis compared farms using traditional irrigation systems with water-saving technologies based on data from 2015–2024.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The agricultural sector of Uzbekistan is the main consumer of water resources, accounting for about 90% of the country's total water consumption. In this regard, the efficiency and modernization of irrigation systems is of strategic importance for the country's economic stability and environmental situation. According to official data for 2005, the area prepared for irrigation was approximately 4,198,000 hectares, of which 3,700,000 hectares were actually irrigated. These figures indicate the extensive coverage of irrigation systems in the country and the high demand for water resources.

In 1994, the efficiency of the irrigation network was approximately 63%, that is, 37 cubic meters of water were lost for every 100 cubic meters of water withdrawn from the source. This clearly demonstrates the need for effective management of water resources and reduction of losses. As a result of monitoring and modernization measures carried out in recent years, a significant increase in efficiency indicators has been observed.

During 2020–2025, great attention was paid to the modernization of irrigation systems in Uzbekistan. In particular, the efficiency of the irrigated area increased through the practical application of drip irrigation, sprinklers and other water-saving technologies. If in 2020 these technologies covered only 4% of irrigated land, by 2025 they reached 50%. At the same time, existing canals and pumping stations were reconstructed and energy-saving and efficient systems were introduced, which allowed reducing water losses by approximately 540 million cubic meters per year.

According to current data, in 2025, the irrigated land area in Uzbekistan will be approximately 4.3 million hectares. Of this, water-saving technologies are used on 413.1 thousand hectares, including 77.3 thousand hectares of drip irrigation, 25.4 thousand hectares of sprinkler irrigation, and 13 thousand hectares of discrete irrigation. These data confirm the positive results of the measures taken to rapidly develop and improve the efficiency of irrigation systems. The analysis shows that if irrigation systems are fully equipped with modern technologies and management systems, the efficiency of water resources use will increase significantly. This will allow increasing agricultural productivity, expanding export potential, and strengthening the country's economic stability. At the same time, there is an opportunity to improve the ecological situation and ensure water security through the widespread introduction of drip irrigation and other water-saving technologies. Thus, the policy implemented to save water resources and modernize irrigation systems has a direct positive impact on the stability of Uzbekistan's agricultural sector and national economic development. Taking into account these analyses, the implementation of the following will lead to independent results:

- Reduce water losses and increase efficiency by replacing aging canals and pumping stations with energy-efficient, automated systems.

- Gradually introduce drip, sprinkler, and discrete irrigation systems to all irrigated areas; especially prioritizing areas with water shortages and where productivity needs to be increased SCADA va raqamli suv boshqaruv tizimlarini keng joriy etish orqali real vaqtda suv resurslarini nazorat qilish, yo'qotishlarni aniqlash va ularni tezkor kamaytirish.

• Along with the modernization of irrigation systems, comprehensively implement measures to monitor soil salinity, drainage, and environmental conditions, and to save water and increase productivity..

• Modernization of irrigation infrastructure through domestic budget funds and foreign investments, including the introduction of modern technologies based on international experience.

If these recommendations are implemented, not only will the efficient use of water resources be ensured, but agricultural productivity will increase, environmental sustainability will be maintained, and the country's export potential will be strengthened.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Modernization of irrigation systems in Uzbekistan's agriculture is of strategic importance for the sustainable development of the agricultural sector. The results of the study show that water-saving technologies not only reduce water consumption, but also serve to increase productivity, improve land reclamation, and maintain ecological balance. At the state policy level, digitalization of water management, ensuring fairness and transparency in water distribution, adapting international experiences to national conditions, and increasing the level of knowledge of farmers are among the urgent tasks. In the future, it will be possible to ensure the country's food security through rational use of water resources, expansion of drip irrigation systems, modernization of water networks, and the use of innovative water-saving technologies.

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